

ROBERT LOUIS STEVENSON'S ROLE IN LITERATURE AND CULTURE

Sokhibova O.N.

Senior teacher at the "Department of Practical English" at the Technical University named after Islam Karimov

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12730874>

Abstract. *Robert Louis Stevenson (1850-1894) is one of the most important figures in the history of literature, whose contribution goes beyond the genres of adventure and romance. This article examines Stevenson's life, his literary works, and their lasting influence on literature and culture. Emphasis is placed on his narrative techniques, thematic research, and the socio-cultural context of his writings.*

Keywords: *scottish literature, Adventure Genre, Historical Novel, Human Psychology, Narrative Techniques, Spiritual Depth, Literary Heritage, Socio-Cultural Influence, Literary Influence, Human Nature Studies, Literary Discovery, Personal Observations*

Robert Louis Stevenson is a Scottish writer, essayist, poet and travel writer. His works such as "Treasure Island" and "The Strange Case of Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde" have left a deep mark on literary and popular culture. This article examines Stevenson's literary career, the thematic depth of his works, and their influence on later literary movements and genres.

Stevenson was born into a family of engineers in Edinburgh, Scotland. His upbringing in affluent surroundings and chronic health problems that forced him to travel to warmer climates deeply influenced his outlook and literary themes. These early experiences are reflected in his travel writings and his interest in the hypocrisy of human nature.

Stevenson's education also contributed greatly to the development of his literary skills. Although he studied law at the University of Edinburgh, his main interest was in literature. During this period, he entered the world of literature, writing many essays and stories.

Stevenson's literary path began with essays and travel writing. His early works, such as *An Inland Journey* (1878) and *A Journey with a Donkey in Seven* (1879), reflect his observational skills and narrative skills. These writings are distinguished by their vivid images and thoughtful tone, which served as a foundation for his later novels.

During this period, Stevenson wrote on a variety of subjects, including travel, historical events, and personal observations. His essays and short stories quickly became popular among readers and helped him establish a unique place in the literary world.

"Treasure Island" (1883) The novel revolutionized the adventure genre, characterized by dynamic characters, a complex plot and a richly described environment. The character of Long John Silver, in particular, demonstrates Stevenson's skill at creating morally complex and stable characters. "Treasure Island" is not only an adventure story for children, but also a deep reflection on human nature and moral dilemma.

The hero of the play, Jim Hawkins, is a boy who lives in a small country hotel in his youth. One day, a mysterious ship captain, Billy Bones, arrives at the hotel. He always hid the treasure map. Before the captain dies, Jim finds the map and shows it to his mother. This map changes Jim's life. Along with Dr. Livesey and Squire Trelawney, Jim and his friends travel to find the treasure. They get on a ship and set off in search of treasure. But among the ship's captain, George

Smollett, and his crew, there is a cunning pirate named Long John Silver who knows about the treasure and wants to steal it. Upon reaching the island, the crew is divided into two groups: Jim and his friends, and Silver and his pirates. Adventures begin on the island, and Jim overcomes many dangers. He reveals the true intentions of Silver and his group. Jim and his friends reach the treasure through difficulties and struggles. Despite Silver's tricks, Jim and his friends find the treasure and succeed.

"The Strange Case of Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde" (1886) the novella is devoted to the study of hypocrisy and human psychology. Stevenson's Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde's depiction of personal fragmentation has become a cultural archetype in literature and psychology. This work raises deep philosophical questions about human inner struggles and hypocrisy and criticizes the moral standards of the Victorian era. The work tells about the mysterious events that happened in London. Mr. Utterson, a lawyer, learns about the strange behavior of his friend, the respected doctor Dr. Henry Jekyll, and the events surrounding the mysterious Mr. Edward Hyde. Hyde is known as a very cruel and criminal person. The Strange Case of Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde has influenced many literary and cultural works. This work has been adapted to theater stages, films and television series for many times. The character of Jekyll and Hyde is popular in modern pop culture and is one of the main characters of the psychological fiction and horror genres.

"The Strange Case of Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde" is an in-depth study of the dual nature of human nature and the inner conflicts of the individual. This short story by Robert Louis Stevenson continues to inspire great interest in its time and today with its psychological depth and mystery. Depicting the struggle between good and evil, the work encourages readers to think and reveals the inner world of man.

"Kidnapped" is a famous adventure novel by Robert Louis Stevenson published in 1886. The play tells the story of the adventures of the young hero David Belfour, reflecting the history and culture of Scotland. The novel was loved by many readers and has been adapted into many films. The play begins with David Belfour being orphaned and meeting his uncle Ebenezer Belfour to claim his rights after his father's death. David goes to live with his uncle to claim his rights, but the uncle tries to kill him and ends up kidnapping him and selling him to the slave ship *Covenant*. "Kidnapped" is one of the classics of the adventure novel genre. The work has been screened many times and adapted to theater scenes. This work has inspired many other writers and artists.

The novel explores Scotland's history and culture, helping to introduce readers to this rich heritage. It also delves into themes of friendship, loyalty, and justice, making it relevant to many readers.

Robert Louis Stevenson's *Kidnapped* is a classic that combines themes of adventure, friendship, and the search for justice. David Belfour's journey full of challenges and dangers will thrill readers and introduce them to the history and culture of Scotland. The work continues to have great influence and is loved by readers today.

In later years, Stevenson's migration to the South Pacific influenced his writing style and themes. Works such as *The Master of Ballantrae* (1889) and *Catriona* (1893) show his mature narrative style and interest in spiritual dilemmas. These works demonstrate his continued exploration of literary discoveries and the complexities of human nature.

Stevenson's move to the South Pacific marked a new phase in his life. During this period, he created many travelogues and novel stories. His life and experiences in the South Pacific brought new colors and themes to his works. Stevenson's works reflect and critique the societal

norms of his time, particularly the Victorian era's emphasis on morality, identity, and progress. His study of the human condition and spiritual uncertainty is still relevant among his contemporaries. Through his writings, Stevenson criticized the moral and cultural norms of Victorian society. His studies of human psychology and hypocrisy have greatly influenced modern literature and philosophy. His works are not only of literary importance, but also raise deep questions about humanity. Robert Louis Stevenson's contributions to literature are important not only for his narrative discoveries but also for his profound thematic research. His works have gone beyond their historical context and become literature that will stand the test of time. Through Stevenson's rich storytelling and insight into human nature, he remains an important figure in literary history. Through his narrative style and the depth of his themes, Stevenson's works remain relevant to contemporary readers and scholars. His adventures and psychological research raise the fundamental questions of humanity and help us to understand them more deeply. Scotland underwent major cultural and social changes in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. During this period, the process of industrialization intensified and the number of people living in cities increased. At the same time, the natural beauty and historical heritage of the countryside has been a source of inspiration for many writers and artists. The neoromantic movement developed in Scotland as a reaction to these processes.

Neo-romanticism was associated with a revival of romanticism and new aesthetic values in Scotland, focusing on natural landscapes, historical themes and the inner world of man. Key representatives of this movement included writers such as Robert Louis Stevenson, James Matthew Barrie, and George MacDonald. Stevenson's works made a great contribution to the development of neoromantic literature. His adventure novels and psychological stories embody the main principles of neoromanticism. Stevenson's works reflect the complexity of human nature and the passion for adventure. Stevenson's work was a source of inspiration not only for his contemporaries, but also for writers and artists of the next generation. His works had a great influence on the development of neo-romanticism and brought the main features of this movement to the general public.

Robert Louis Stevenson's contribution to neoromanticism is large and important. His works reflect the main principles of neoromanticism, reflecting naturalness, emotions, adventure and inner conflict. Stevenson's work greatly influenced the development of neo-romantic literature and brought the main features of this movement to the general public. His works have not lost their importance even today and are highly appreciated by literary critics.

REFERENCES

1. Calder, Jenny. "Robert Louis Stevenson: A Life Study." New York: Oxford University Press, 1980.
2. Daiches, David. "Robert Louis Stevenson and His World". London: Thames & Hudson, 1973.
3. Furnas, JC "Voyage to Windward: The Life of Robert Louis Stevenson." New York: William Sloane Associates, 1951.
4. Menikoff, Barry. "Narrating Scotland: The Imagination of Robert Louis Stevenson". Columbia: University of South Carolina Press, 2005.
5. Sandison, Alan. "Robert Louis Stevenson and the Appearance of Modernism: A Future Feeling." London: Macmillan, 1996.
6. Harman, Claire. "Robert Louis Stevenson: A Biography". New York